

A Survey on Wikipedia Awareness and Use by Academic Librarians of Abuja Municipal Nigeria.

FOLASADE ADEPOJU, ABDULLAHI BALA BALA SHEHU

A Survey on Wikipedia Awareness and Use by Academic Librarians of Abuja Municipal Nigeria.

FOLASADE ADEPOJU

National Library of Nigeria

E-mail: folasadeadepoju@gmail.com

Phone no: + 2347032636297

Abstract

This study was carried out to investigate the awareness and use of Wikipedia by Academic Librarians situated in Abuja municipal of Nigeria. 5 research objectives guided the study, and the population of the study consists of the entire census of Academic Librarians working in University Libraries situated in Abuja, semi-structured questionnaire was the instrument of data collection, and a descriptive method of analysis was used to analyze the data. Findings show that Librarians are aware of and utilizing Wikipedia

but for personal endeavors and have positive as well as negative perspectives toward Wikipedia. It was discovered that Academic Librarians of Abuja are cautious in referring patrons to Wikipedia in the course of their professional duties, and at the same skeptical to use it as a service delivery option and in conducting research, they attributed the difficulty of evaluating Wikipedia information as the major hindering factor; but generally, they utilize and frequent Wikipedia sites. The study advocates proper channeling of the initiative and partnership between the Wikimedia Foundation and AFLIA on skill impact to create and edit Wikipedia content as it will go a long way in eradicating the negative impression.

Keywords: Wikipedia, ICT, University Libraries, Abuja Nigeria

Introduction

Unending innovations in information and communication technology (ICT) have ushered in transformations characterized by the availability of various Library and Learning applications, Open Educational Resources, and Knowledge Repositories among others. All these have altered the way libraries and librarians provide information services, access information, and conduct research, and process information resources. Wikipedia is one of such avenues that librarians use for innovative information services. Wikipedia is an open-source knowledge repository with the incorporation of various resources and functions that enhance digital Study, Information access, and Information Literacy in the same vein Wikipedia is a free, web-based encyclopedia running on wiki technology, a technology that allows anyone to quickly create or edit and modify web pages. Wikipedia has a huge lot of content, having to date approximately 7.9 million articles in 253 languages (Luyt et al 2008) Unlike other open-access databases which have more stringent review processes involving subject experts and professional editors, Wikipedia relies on collaborative effort of volunteers, sourcing its content from more than 75,000 active contributors, practically anyone with an account and internet connection, The upside to this is that anyone who wants to contribute may do so, and articles are updated quickly, in fact, having the ability to unfold as events happen, according to Soules (2015) students flock to it, but faculty views including Academic Librarians are mixed have the perspective that Wikipedia is not a good reference source for research. Going further Osadebe et al (2022) observed that the use of Wikipedia and its sister projects by academics for research most especially in the African context is not encouraged, it is believed that the sources are not reliable, especially the fact that it is editable by anyone regardless of geographical location, Nevertheless, as the quality, scope, and usefulness of Wikipedia increase, it has become imperative to explore its usage as a reference source by academic librarians for learning and research, as an integral part of open access and open knowledge source and as a reliable alternative for information service delivery to the clientele of academic libraries. This study seeks to investigate the usage of Wikipedia as a reference source during library service delivery and if it is consulted by Academic Librarians when carrying out research. few articles exist on Wikipedia awareness and utilization, from the librarian's perspective, and practically non in the African context which necessitates this study to fill the gap.

Objectives of the study

- To find out if Abuja Academic Librarians are Using Wikipedia
- Investigate Academic Librarians situated in Abuja Municipal perspective on Wikipedia
- To Find out if Academic Librarians situated in Abuja Municipal index Wikipedia as a Database for Information query
- To find out if Academic Librarians situated in Abuja Municipal consult Wikipedia when offering references and other services to their respective clientele
- To find out if Academic Librarians utilize Wikipedia when conducting research.
- To identify challenges associated with Wikipedia usage by Academic Librarians

Review of Related Literature review

This study adopts a Descriptive and Integrative type of literature review, it is based on the recency of the literature, few articles exist on Wikipedia awareness and utilization, and practically non in the African context. The review of the literature highlights the various studies which provide an overview of research studies on Wikipedia use and awareness arranged chronologically.

Osadepe et al (2022) examined the edit A thon initiative granted by Wikimedia to create awareness and usage in UNN University Library interviews and a questionnaire was used as a means of data collection, the finding shows that Wikimedia edit -a thon initiative creates awareness and usage of Wikipedia by academics.

Li & Thelwal (2021) This recent study investigated the perceptions of academic librarians regarding Wikipedia's use by students and researchers. The authors surveyed 161 librarians from various US institutions and found that while many librarians recognize the benefits of Wikipedia as a starting point for research, they also have concerns about its accuracy and reliability. The study also found that librarians who use Wikipedia themselves are more likely to encourage its use by students and researchers.

Bordelon and Chang (2020) examined the perceptions of undergraduate students towards Wikipedia and how their use of the platform affected their information literacy development. The authors surveyed 297 students at a US university and found that while many students used

Wikipedia as a starting point for research, they also recognized its limitations and relied on other sources to verify information found on the platform.

Mills and Baur (2019) Investigate the use of Wikipedia in academic libraries, including its role in information literacy instruction and the challenges it presents to librarians. The authors argue that while Wikipedia can be a valuable resource for students, it is important for librarians to educate their users about its limitations and to encourage them to verify information found on Wikipedia using other sources.

Wang et al (2018) The study examines the use of Wikipedia in research and identifies the benefits and limitations of the platform. The authors highlight the need for greater understanding among researchers and librarians about Wikipedia's strengths and weaknesses and the importance of verifying information found on the platform using other sources.

Glies and Bolacker (2017) This study evaluates the quality of Wikipedia articles with missing references using a random sample of 5,000 articles. The authors found that while the majority of articles had at least one missing reference, the quality of articles with missing references was generally similar to that of articles with complete references. The study highlights the importance of verifying information found on Wikipedia and the need for more robust citation practices on the platform.

Jeng and Heish (2016) This study explores the perceptions of academic librarians in the United States and the United Kingdom towards Wikipedia, including their participation in editing and contributing to Wikipedia. The authors found that while many librarians are aware of Wikipedia and its limitations, few have contributed to or edited Wikipedia articles. The study highlights the need for greater participation by librarians in the development of Wikipedia as a reliable reference source.

Choi et al (2015) found that users often use Wikipedia to obtain background information on a topic before proceeding to more in-depth sources.

The literature reviewed shows that while Wikipedia is a widely used reference source, knowledge database concerns remain about its accuracy, reliability, and information creation.

Scope and Limitation of the Study

The scope of the present study is limited to the university libraries situated in Abuja Municipal of Nigeria and the respondents are Academic Librarians, other cadres such Para professional and Non-professional are excluded from this survey because Academic Librarians are the ones in charge of professional duties and service delivery to clientele, in addition, the researchers could not access one of the selected universities located in Abuja Municipal, which was the University of Abuja, the university was shut down at the time the researchers visited, because on an ongoing nationwide election.

Methods

The research design of this study was a descriptive survey and non-probability sampling, specifically purposive sampling, was used to select university libraries situated in Abuja Municipal. the population was made up of the entire census of Academic Librarians working in University Libraries situated in Abuja Municipal, these University Libraries include Baze University, Nile University African University of Science Technology, Philomath University, Veritas University, and the University of Abuja, however, the researchers could not access the University of Abuja due to factors beyond their control. A semi-structured questionnaire was used to elicit information from the respondents, The purpose of the questionnaire was to obtain data regarding the Awareness and Use of Wikipedia in Abuja Municipal University Libraries. A total of 30 questionnaires were retrieved and found usable to cut across all university libraries situated in Abuja Municipal except University of Abuja. Data collected were analyzed using frequency counts and percentages.

Demographic Information

Table 1: Profile of the Respondents N=30

Gender	BU		NU		AUST		VU		PU	
	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%
Male	5	41.7	5	71	-		2	33	1	33
Female	7	58.3	2	29	2	100	4	67	2	67
Total	12	100	7	100	2	100	6	100	3	100
Cum Total		40		23		7		20		10

Key Words: BU: Baze University NU: Nile University AUST: African University of Science and Technology, PU: Philomath University

From Table 1 The total number of Academic Librarians cutting across all the selected universities is 30, Baze University has the highest number of respondents (12) at 40% followed by Nile University (7) at 23%, African University of Science and Technology had the least number of respondent (2) 7%, Veritas University, and Philomath University had (6) 20% and 3(10%) respectively.

Table 2: Academic Degree

Qualifications	N=30	%
Doctorate	3	10
Master's	17	57
Bachelor's	10	33

Higher National Diploma	-	
Total	30	100

Table 2 shows the Academic qualification of Abuja Librarians (3) 10% had a Doctorate, 17 (57%) had a Master's and (10) 33% had a Bachelor's non had a Higher national Diploma with this qualification, the respondents were expected to give valid information on "Wikipedia Use" in their respective Academic Libraries.

Wikipedia Awareness Usage and Perspective by Abuja Academic Librarians.

Table 3: Perspective View of Librarians towards Wikipedia

Statement	N=30	%
Lack of citations or sources		
Inaccurate or unreliable information		
Good Information source		
Provides up to date information		
Provides a quick overview of a topic.	12	40
Covers a Wide range of topics.	10	33
Biased or Incomplete information.	8	27
Other specify		

The perspective of Abuja Librarians was sought towards Wikipedia utilization in rendering Library services both negative and positive was indicated to have an overview of Abuja Academic Librarians' Perspective towards Wikipedia Utilization, from Table 3 Abuja Academic Librarians (12) 40% indicated that Wikipedia provides a quick overview of topics (10) 33% indicates that Wikipedia covers a wide range of topics and (8) 27% believes that Wikipedia information is biased and incomplete.

Usage of Wikipedia

Table 4: Do you use Wikipedia

Item Statement	N=30	%
Yes	10	33
No	2	7
Usage in some fashion	18	60

From Table 4 Respondents were asked if they utilize Wikipedia (10) 33% indicated they use Wikipedia, (2) 7% indicated they do not use Wikipedia, (18) 60% indicated they use Wikipedia in some fashion, the result aligns with the finding of LI and Thewal (2021) who found out that Librarians in United stated use Wikipedia but have some reservations.

Table 5: Frequency of Wikipedia Usage

Frequency	N=30	%
Multiple times a day	1	3
Once a Day	-	
A few times a week	20	66
Once a week	9	30
Rarely	-	
Never	-	

Table 5 indicates the Frequency of Usage of Wikipedia results show that respondents use Wikipedia a few times a week as indicated by (20) 66% while (9) 30% indicate they use Wikipedia once a week, only (1) 3% indicated that they use Wikipedia daily. This goes against the findings of Bordelion and Chang (2020) that faculty, librarians, and students use Wikipedia daily to satisfy their information needs.

Table 6: Reasons for using Wikipedia

Item Statement	N=30	%
Starting point research		
Gain background information on a topic	28	84
Leisure reading	1	3
Entertainment	1	3

Independent Learning	-	
Others specify		

Table 6 summarizes reasons for the usage of Wikipedia by Academic Librarians in Abuja, Most of the Librarians from the survey use Wikipedia to gain background information with 84% indicating so, others are for Leisure reading and Entertainment 3% respectively. This goes against the finding of Synder (2013) and LI and Thelwal (2021) whose finding depicts that Librarians use Wikipedia for Research and Independent learning.

Table 7: Reason for not using Wikipedia

Item Statement	N=30	%
Not a reliable source of Information	30	100
Anyone can- edit	20	67
Always use Google	10	33
Do not Need		
Others Specify		

From Table 7 Respondents' reason for not using Wikipedia was sought the question also specified to check as necessary, Academic Librarians identified Not- reliable sources and anyone can edit as the reason for not using Wikipedia, 33%percent indicated they use Google for information services these align closely with findings Wang et al (2018) **Table 8: Librarian Awareness of Wikipedia Categories**

Item Statement	N=30	%
Aware_Edited_Anyone	30	100

Aware of Wikipedia's sister projects such as wikicommons, wiki cloud, Wikiversity, wiki tech, etc.	10	33
Wiki protected pages	1	3
Wiki-edit a thon activity	10	33
Others specify		

The researcher wanted to find out if the Abuja Academic Librarians are aware of Wikimedia projects and other features and activities of Wikipedia, respondents were asked to check all, if necessary, Table 7 depicts Academic Librarians are aware that Wikipedia pages can be edited by anyone (30) 100% (10) 33% are aware of Edit thon initiative to create Wikipedia awareness and (1) 3% indicated awareness of protected Wikipedia pages. This is in line with the findings of Osadepe et al (2022) who investigated the activities surrounding Wikipedia- edit-a-Thon at the University of Nigeria.

Wikipedia Usefulness to Abuja Academic Librarians

Table 9: The usefulness of Wikipedia

Item statement	N=30	%
Very Useful	10	33
Somewhat Useful	20	67
Not Very Useful	-	
Not at all Useful	-	

From Table 9 33% (10) found Wikipedia content to be very useful and (20) 67% Found it somewhat useful this finding aligns with Luyt et al (2010) findings indicating that Wikipedia was overall a useful information tool in Singapore and overall librarians in Singapore has a positive upbeat.

Wikipedia Usage

Table 10: Inclusion of Wikipedia as a Library Database for N=30

Yes	No
	(30) 100 %

Table 10 aims to solicit information on the inclusion of Wikipedia as a Library database indexed on the Library URL home page. The finding shows that (30) 100% that Wikipedia is not part of their Library Database, which shows a negative attitude toward Wikipedia usage as an information resource.

Table 11: Wikipedia for Service Delivery N=30

Item Statement	N=30	%
Rarely	25	83
Sometimes	5	17
Often		
Very often		

Table 11 findings show that (25) 83% rarely use Wikipedia for service delivery in the library and (5) 17% indicate that they sometimes use Wikipedia for service delivery which aligns with the findings of Li and Thelwal (2021) that Librarian in the USA do not utilize Wikipedia for Library information service because they are concerned with the Accuracy and source of information.

Table 12 Capacity of Wikipedia Usage

Item Statement	N=30	%
Research	2	6
Learning and Teaching		
Service Delivery		
Entertainment and Leisure		
Others specify		

From Table 12 only (2) 6% use Wikipedia for research.

Table 13: Usage of Wikipedia for Offering Library Services

Item Statement	N=30	%
Reference Service	-	
Information Literacy	10	33
Digital Competence	1	3
Others specify		

Finding from table 13 shows (10) 33% and (1) 3% of Librarians use Wikipedia for information literacy and Digital competence, this finding in line with Luyt (2010) Librarians believe that Wikipedia has a lot of inaccurate information that is the reason they do not use Wikipedia to offer information services to their respective clientele

Table 14: Challenges of Wikipedia Usage as a Resource

Item Statement	N=30	%
Difficulty in evaluating the reliability of the information	30	100

Difficulty in finding a credible source	-	
Lack of understanding of Wikipedia policy	-	

From Table 14 finding shows that the Major challenge impeding Wikipedia utilization is the Difficulty in evaluating the reliability of the information with all the respondents indicating it (30) 100 % this finding is in line with Borsellino and Chang (2020)

Conclusion

The Abuja Academic librarians were generally cautious in referring patrons to Wikipedia in the course of their professional duties, and at the same skeptical to use it as a service delivery option, they otherwise gave a range of mostly positive responses and negative responses. This is an indication that the potential of Wikipedia can be fully harnessed All the surveyed Librarians for this study were aware of Wikipedia, and Use Wikipedia for personal endeavors, many have either visited the site or used its services even though quite a number indicated that they used Wikipedia for entertainment and leisure rather than used for information services, This indicates that librarians in this study are cautious in advocating for Wikipedia in their work life, but utilize it in their personal information quests. The cautionary use of Wikipedia by Librarians is most likely driven by awareness of the negative aspects of Wikipedia. These negative issues have given way to new editing policies and article creation policies to strengthen the content of Wikipedia. Going further the perspective view of Abuja Academic Librarians have a positive view toward Wikipedia with 40% indicating that Wikipedia provides a quick overview of a topic and 33% indicating Wikipedia covers a wide range of topics but indicated that the major reason for not adopting Wikipedia for Professional service is difficulty in evaluating the reliability of the information, this is already remedied by the initiative of Wikimedia and partnership with AFLIA by equipping Librarians with skills to participate in editing and adding content to Wikipedia, and various new policies, All that is essential is proper channeling and awareness campaign to remedy the negative impression toward Wikipedia.

References

- Bordelon, A. M., & Chang, C. (2020). Student perceptions of Wikipedia and their information literacy development. *Journal of Academic Librarianship*, 46(3).
- Giles, J., & Bollacker, K. (2017). Evaluating the quality of Wikipedia articles with missing references. *PloS one*, 12(8).
- Li, J., & Thelwall, M. (2021). Wikipedia and academic librarians: perceived benefits and concerns. *Journal of Librarianship and Information Science*, 52(4), 1061-1075.
- Luyt, B., Zainal, C. Z. B. C., Mayo, O. V. P., & Yun, T. S. (2008). Youth Perception and Usage of Wikipedia. *Information Research*, 13(4).
- Mills, C., & Baur, K. (2019). Unpacking the use of Wikipedia in academic libraries. *Journal of Academic Librarianship*, 45(2), 97-103.
- Osadebe, N. E., Ukwoma, S. C., Njoku, E. O., Udochukwu, D. C., Madumere, C., & Ezeani, C. N. (2022). Wikipedia edit-a-thon in a Nigerian academic library. *Library Philosophy & Practice*. (eJournal).
- Snyder, J. (2013). Wikipedia: Librarians' perspectives on its use as a reference source. *Reference and User Services Quarterly*, 53(2), 155-163.
- Soules, A. (2015). Faculty perception of Wikipedia in the California state university system. *New Library World*, 116(3/4), 213-226.
- Wang, X., Li, Y., Li, X., & Zhang, X. (2018). The use of Wikipedia in research: A review of literature. *Journal of Educational Technology Development and Exchange (JETDE)*, 11(1), 1-14.